

Inclusive Finance: Fueling India's Journey to a USD 5 Trillion Economy

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Abstract: India aims to transform into 'Viksit Bharat' by 2047 during the 'Amrit kaal' period, setting a landmark goal of achieving a \$5 trillion economy by 2027-28. This ambitious objective necessitates the active participation of every citizen in nation-building. Financial inclusion stands as a pivotal pillar in any economy, crucial for fostering economic growth by ensuring affordable access to financial services for vulnerable and marginalized sectors of society. This inclusivity in the financial system significantly boosts economic activity by facilitating the mobilization of savings and funds for investments, thereby enhancing consumption and income levels across the economy. The introduction of PMJDY marked a critical step towards this goal. This study explores how financial inclusion can catalyze India's path to a \$5 trillion economy, emphasizing the importance of comprehensive financial services encompassing banking, insurance, and pension products. It also underscores the role of financial literacy in promoting broader financial inclusion. Moreover, the paper addresses challenges within the financial sector that hinder growth prospects and proposes strategies to overcome these barriers. The paper employs descriptive methodology based on secondary data to examine the significance of financial inclusion in realizing India's economic ambitions. The findings of the study underscore the imperative of advancing financial inclusion efforts to foster more equitable economic growth.

Index Terms: Financial Inclusion, Financial services, Economic growth, \$5 trillion economy, Financial Literacy, PMJDY

I. INTRODUCTION

In 2019, our esteemed Prime Minister set forth an ambitious vision to elevate India's GDP to \$5 trillion by 2025. However, due to the pandemic, this target was subsequently extended to the fiscal year 2027-28. India has been steadfastly progressing towards achieving this goal. Presently, the Indian economy stands at approximately \$3.7 trillion, making it the 5th largest economy in nominal terms and boasting the 4th largest stock market with a valuation of \$4 trillion.

Achieving a \$5 trillion economy is not merely about accumulating trillions of dollars in the treasury. Its true essence lies in building the capacity and capabilities of the economy to grow on a sustainable path of growth. By building capabilities it means enhancing the socio-economic welfare of each and every individual of the nation. Which can only be possible by inclusion of all in the nation building. Financial Inclusion has been one such policy priority of the government in the recent past. According to the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), Financial Inclusion involves ensuring that marginalized groups, including those in vulnerable sections and lower-income brackets, can access financial products and services at a reasonable price. These services should be offered in a fair and transparent manner by conventional financial institutions. Its goal is to furnish individuals with resources like savings accounts, credit options, insurance policies, and digital payment platforms. This empowers them to interact with the formal financial system, effectively handle their finances, and cultivate financial competence. Hence, achieving financial inclusion is one of the top policy priority for inclusive growth and the launch of flagship scheme – Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) is a step towards that direction. PMJDY was announced on August 15, 2014, and officially launched on August 28, 2014. As reported by the Press Information Bureau, GOI (2023), on the ninth anniversary of the PMJDY scheme, the number of accounts has surged by 3.4 times, the number rose from 14.72 crore in March 2015 to August 2023, reaching 50.09 crore. As per the Global Findex Database (2021), global account ownership has attained a rate of 76 percent among the worldwide population and 71 percent among individuals in developing countries. Whereas, Indian account ownership stands at 78 percent, higher than the global average representing the efforts of governmental schemes like PMJDY in achieving the milestone.

The technological trinity of Jan Dhan, Aadhar and Mobile (JAM Trinity) has revolutionized the process of inclusion in an efficient and transparent manner. Through the proper identification of beneficiaries and direct access to them,

technology plays an instrumental role. This not only ensures efficient targeting but also saves significant funds for the nation by averting misallocation. It is evident from above that government initiatives such as the implementation of PMJDY, JAM Trinity, and the Digitalization of Financial Services have not only been instrumental in strengthening the Indian financial system but also guarantee the inclusion of all segments of society.

Now, the question arises what role will Indian Financial Sector play to achieve USD 5 trillion target? With the world's largest population, India possesses the largest portion of the working-age populace. A robust and transparent financial sector can aid in the efficient mobilization and allocation of funds- a pre-requisite for realizing the USD 5 trillion Indian economy. Financial intermediaries and financial markets are indispensable for fostering a vibrant and growing economy. This research paper is a modest attempt to determine the importance of Financial Inclusion in achieving the target of USD 5 trillion Indian economy. The study examines the necessity for Financial Inclusion, identifies the challenges, and explores potential avenues to address these challenges.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Rural India Road to US \$5 Trillion Economy (2018) PHDCCI, the report underscored the significance of PMJDY as a government policy initiative in streamlining the economy, granting access to various financial services such as bank deposit accounts and credit, and in the future, even insurance and pension. This is deemed an essential step towards reaching the goal of a USD 5 trillion economy. **Economic Survey (2019)** laid down 8 percent as the required rate of real GDP growth to attain a sustainable growth path. It also “makes the case for investment, especially private investment as key driver, that drives demand, creates capacity, increases labor productivity, introduces new technology and generate jobs”. **Prof. Subhendu Bhattacharya**, Achieving a GDP of 5 trillion Dollars and surpassing that milestone will occur through the execution of policy measures that prioritize reform-oriented activities, foster coordination among sectors, integrate technology, optimize resource utilization, and promote value based production. **Yan Carrière-Swallow, Vikram Haksar and Manasa Patnam (2021)**, in their working paper explicitly indicates that the integration of various banking and non-banking entities into a unified infrastructure has the potential to foster inclusive finance, as demonstrated by the rise in transactions involving numerous transactions with relatively small monetary amounts. The comprehensive architecture of digital infrastructures made available to the public has the capacity to enable the delivery of numerous financial services and enhance both financial inclusion and economic growth. According to **Dr. Ranganath G (2022)**, as the government strives to become 3rd largest economy by 2024-25, several difficulties must be adequately addressed. To meet the growing ambitions of India's current young, the government needs to focus on policies for good governance and establish a strong, wealthy, and inclusive India. As per the latest report by **PHDCCI (2024)**, banking and financial sector have ability to play is pivotal in achieving the target of \$5 trillion GDP therefore government should incentivize them in enhancing their robustness so that they can aid small businesses to expand their capabilities according to the demand trajectory. As stated by the **Finance Minister in Vibrant Gujarat Global Summit (2024)**, the urgent requirement is the collaborative actions of People, Stakeholders and Central Government in achieving the target in 2027-28 and further the long term target of \$30 trillion by 2047.

III. OBJECTIVES

1. To analyze the importance of financial inclusion and identify how it contributes to reaching the objective of a USD 5 trillion economy.
2. To identify the challenges associated with the financial sector impeding the growth prospects.
3. To explore potential avenues to address the challenges.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The data for this study is collected from a variety of sources including, but not limited to, The Handbook of Statistics on the Indian economy (2023) published by the Reserve Bank of India, the Report on Trends and Progress of Indian Banking by RBI, Annual reports from regulatory bodies, the Global Findex database (2021) of the World Bank, as well as reports, journals, and published articles. This research paper employs a descriptive approach to fulfill its objectives through the analysis of secondary data. Tables, figures, and charts are used for the interpretation of data in the study.

V. NEED FOR FINANCIAL INCLUSION

Inclusive growth has been a central focus of Indian governments since the early 20th century. Mahatma Gandhi emphasized the importance of inclusive growth by promoting the concept of "Sarvodaya through Antyodaya," while the current government's slogan of "Sabka Saath Sabka Vikaas" continues this tradition. Financial Inclusion represents one of the steps taken towards fostering inclusive growth.

Chart 1: The Virtuous Cycle of Savings, Investment and Growth.

The financial sector is vital in driving economic growth for any economy. The utilization of financial services significantly impacts economic activity by facilitating the smooth mobilization of savings and funds available for investments. This process results in increased production due to higher capital formation, which further enhances consumption and income for the economy. Ultimately, this cycle contributes to higher economic growth.

Leveraging Financial Inclusion for India's \$5 Trillion Economy: India in the second decade of 21st century has been experiencing a larger middle class population. According to estimates published by PRICE's ICE 360⁰ pan India primary survey, the extent of the Indian middle class has been steadily increasing. The middle-class population (with an annual income ranging from 5 lakh to 30 lakh) is projected to rise from 31 percent of the population in 2020-21 to 61 percent in 2046-47. According to paper published by Asian Development Bank, there is evidence that a larger middle class is associated with higher levels of savings in a country. Effective mobilization of savings necessitates the inclusion of the middle class in the banking sector to ensure that these savings are not wasted. This process can initiate a virtuous cycle of savings, investments, and growth.

VI. FINANCIAL INCLUSION: CATALYST FOR GREATER AND BALANCED GROWTH

As per the RBI, Financial Inclusion refers to the process of providing accessible financial services to vulnerable and disadvantaged segments of society at an affordable cost. These services encompass banking, insurance, pension, postal, and investment services. An individual is considered financially included if they have access to all these financial services. Now the researcher will endeavor to explore avenues through which access to these financial services can contribute to economic growth, which is essential for achieving the target of a \$5 trillion economy.

Banking Services: The services provided by banking institutions are crucial in resource accumulation. Financial inclusion is instrumental in ensuring the collection of resources increases steadily. Therefore, comprehending the current status of these services and the contribution made by financial inclusion in driving sustainable growth becomes crucial. Status of Banking and Non-Banking products: Banking and savings related products are considered as the key component among the overall financial products and services from the perspective of financial inclusion. According to the data published by NCFE-FLIS 2019, all over India 15 percent of the people are financially included (having access of both banking and non-banking products). It also emphasized the fact that 87 percent of the population have been included in savings related banking products (Savings Account, Fixed Deposit Account and recurring Deposit Account) whereas only 16 percent of the population have included in Non-banking Products (Insurance, Pension, capital market products etc.) highlighting a vast difference between the two categories and also reducing the overall percentage of financially included in India.

Figure 1: Distribution of people having access to Banking and Non-Banking products

Source: NCFE-FLIS 2019

Urban people have higher percentage of inclusion in both banking and non-banking products. Increasing the inclusion of individuals in accessing non-banking products also becomes necessary to enhance the overall level of financial inclusion.

Credit-Deposit Ratio: is a metric that represents the amount of deposits mobilized by a bank that has been lent out where a lower ratio suggests that banks are underutilizing their deposits. According to the RBI's Report on Trends and Progress in the Indian economy, the CDR has improved from 71 percent in 2022 to 75.1 percent in 2023, attributed to the financial inclusion initiatives implemented by the government. It can be inferred from the improved CDR that banks have been actively lending the deposited funds, which is expected to have a positive impact on the virtuous cycle of savings and investment. While a higher CDR ratio can indicate increased lending activity by banks, which in turn may stimulate economic activity and potentially contribute to GDP growth. A higher CDR ratio can be indicative of a healthy banking system.

Status of PMJDY Accounts: As on ninth anniversary of PMJDY in August 2023, a record of 50.09 crore accounts have been opened under the scheme representing the increased access to banking and allied services. According to the Report on Trends and Progress of Indian Banking by RBI, since the introduction of the PMJDY in 2014, the number of accounts held by both men and women in the household sector – especially loan accounts – has been steadily increasing. Although there are fewer women-owned loan and deposit accounts in comparison with their male counterparts, the former have been increasing at a much faster pace. For any economy to grow at full potential it requires the cooperation of each and every individual at equal strengths. This necessitates more and more financial inclusion of specially the vulnerable sections such as women and weaker sections to appropriate the desired results of financial inclusion.

Figure 2: Demographic Progress in Financial Inclusion

Credits: Report on trends and Progress of Indian Banking (2023), RBI

Pension Products: Pension funds induce long-term retirement savings, mobilize the same from the savings market and create assets by investing in the capital market. The fund managers provide the choice to the customers to invest in various funds. By encouraging the people to increase their investment levels in equities would have a massive impact on capital market and on the economy as a whole. According to the NCFE-FLIS 2019 report, pension products have

the lowest level of attractiveness among the population, with only 12 percent of people having access to pension products in rural areas and 15 percent in urban areas. As per the Annual Report of PFRDA (2022-23), since the introduction of NPS, and more recently APY, the pension sector has expanded in India. Total number of subscribers have increased over three-fold from 1.5 crore in March 2017 to over 5.2 crore by March 2022. In terms of numbers it is dominated by Atal Pension Scheme (APY). Pension schemes serve as instruments for long-term savings, highlighting the importance for policymakers to prioritize efforts to enhance their attractiveness.

Insurance services: Insurance as a financial tool acts a barrier against the unforeseen future losses which can affect individual's wealth and future income-generating capacities. Insurance Penetration is considered as key tools for assessing the potential and development of insurance sector. India's overall insurance penetration reduced to 4 per cent in 2022-23 from the level of 4.2 per cent in 2021-22. In terms of penetration, India is far behind the global average of 7% of the GDP. Therefore, fostering greater insurance penetration in the economy is essential for enhancing its efficiency, thereby bolstering a sustainable trajectory of growth.

Financial Literacy: It has been considered as one of the pillars of financial inclusion. Financially literate individuals have the ability to make knowledgeable financial decisions, thereby enhancing their well-being. In India, the National Centre for Financial Education (NCFE) is responsible for conducting the Financial Literacy and Inclusion Survey.

Table 1: Financial Literacy in India (in terms of percent)

Year	Male	Female	Rural	Urban	Overall
2013-14	23	16	15	25	20
2018-19	29	21	24	33	27

Source: NCLE-FLIS of 2013-14 and 2018-19

Based on data available for the periods 2013-14 and 2018-19, the overall level of financial literacy in India has increased from 20 percent to 27 percent. However, there is still room for improvement in this area.

VII. CHALLENGES

Following are the challenges related to financial inclusion that could impede growth prospects in India:

Quantity Vs Quality

PMJDY was launched with a mission to eradicate widespread financial exclusion. Since its inception, the PMJDY has witnessed a record-breaking number of account openings. According to a working paper by the IMF in 2020, a total of 404 million accounts had been opened under the PMJDY, with 86 percent of these accounts still operative. The remaining 14 percent were classified as inoperative, leading to the dormancy of these accounts.

Figure 3: Share of operative PMJDY accounts

Credits: Digital Financial Services and Inclusion (IMF)

The stagnation of the share of operative accounts, as depicted in Figure 3, indicates a decline in the quality of financial inclusion. This trend should be carefully examined and addressed by policymakers. While PMJDY has achieved success in quantitative terms, the qualitative aspect still lags behind.

Low Financial Literacy

According to the survey published by the NCFE, the financial literacy level for the entire country stood at 27 percent in 2018-19. Based on available data for 2013-14 and 2018-19, it is apparent that the overall level of financial literacy in India is still in its nascent stages. Furthermore, the rate of improvement in financial literacy among males surpasses that among females. Rural areas notably lag behind in terms of financial literacy, which is concerning given India's substantial rural population.

Source: NCFE-FLIS of 2013-14 and 2018-19

Addressing low financial literacy is crucial as it poses a significant obstacle to achieving the desired outcomes of financial inclusion in driving economic growth.

Declining role of Social Security Products in Financial Inclusion

Social security has a vital role in providing protection to the people of a country. Within the realm of financial inclusion, insurance and pension products are categorized as non-banking financial services. At present India's insurance penetration is approximately 4 percent of the GDP.

Source: Annual Reports of IRDAI

Figure-5, illustrates a decline in the penetration of insurance services as a percentage of GDP since 2020-21. Furthermore, India falls significantly below the global average of 7% of GDP, indicating a low insurance penetration rate. Inadequate awareness about insurance is identified as one of the primary reasons behind this low penetration in India. Likewise, the pension sector in India is experiencing a downward trajectory. According to the Global Pension Index (2023), India ranked 45th out of 47 countries indicating a dire state of affairs in the pension sector. Key factors contributing to the underperformance of the Indian pension sector include the skewed coverage of pension schemes, which predominantly target the organized sector, lower returns offered by these schemes, and a lack of awareness about available schemes. To enhance the overall index value of India's pension system, measures such as introducing a minimum level of support for the most financially vulnerable elderly individuals and expanding the coverage of pension arrangements to include the unorganized working class are imperative.

VIII. RECOMMENDATIONS

Stepping Up of Structural Reform

Traditionally, the Indian economy's capital market has relied on volatile capital inflows from foreign investors, which have a significant impact on investment sentiment. Given this scenario, reforms should be implemented to enhance gross domestic investments. Enhancing financial inclusion necessitates a heightened focus on structural reforms. The reforms, characterized by technological advancements and increased liberalization, aim to bolster institutional capacity for mobilizing domestic savings, promote competition among banks, facilitate new market entrants, and fortify the stability of the financial sector.

Tapping the Leakages via Financial Inclusion

The recent announcement in the Interim Budget 2024 highlighted the success of PMJDY in preventing leakages of approximately 2.7 lakh crore through Direct Benefit Transfer (DBT). This underscores the importance of DBT in efficiently disbursing funds. There should be a greater integration of government schemes into the DBT framework, encouraging more people to open bank accounts to receive benefits directly into their accounts rather than in kind. This shift would ultimately promote more financially prudent expenditure among beneficiaries.

Effective Financial Inclusion is the need of the hour

When discussing financial inclusion, the primary focus is often on increased access to fundamental banking services such as deposits, savings, and remittances. However, other aspects of financial inclusion, such as pension, insurance, and wealth management, are equally crucial. Despite their significance, these dimensions are still in their nascent stages, and there is a lack of sufficient data concerning them. Effective financial inclusion necessitates broad access to a wide range of financial services. Policy makers and regulators should focus on making financial services attractive to the people without causing any dent to the profitability of the suppliers of the services.

IX. CONCLUSION

“Growth is never by mere chance; it is the result of forces working together”. In addition to other sectors, the financial sector also plays a pivotal role in the economic growth of any nation. Financial sector to stimulate economic growth effectively, it requires proper mobilization of resources. Financial inclusion guarantees that every individual in society plays a vital role in nation-building. It enables the mobilization of funds by providing access to both banking and non-banking financial products. In the Indian context, evidence suggests instances of financial exclusion, particularly concerning non-banking financial products, especially in rural areas. Pervasive financial illiteracy, unappealing non-banking services and inoperative bank accounts under PMJDY scheme are among the significant challenges associated with financial inclusion. The call of the moment is effective financial inclusion, which guarantees that individuals have access to a diverse array of financial services. The collective efforts of all members of society are necessary for India to attain sustainable economic growth of \$5 trillion.

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